

CHARACTERISTICS OF ORGANIZING INDEPENDENT WORK BASED ON A COMPETENT APPROACH

Torayeva Gavharbonu Talibjonovna

Tashkent State Pedagogical University researcher

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10026190>

***Abstract.** The article discusses the features of independent work organization of students of higher education institutions based on a competent approach, the problems encountered in this process.*

***Keywords:** competent approach, pedagogical situation, education, independent education, organizational ability, competence, modern approaches.*

INTRODUCTION

One of the main tasks of higher education is to form a creative personality of a specialist who has social demand and is capable of independent work, independent development and innovative activity. Solving this problem is possible only by moving from the teaching paradigm to the educational paradigm. The reform of higher professional education, which is being carried out today, is related to this.

It is necessary to transform the student from a passive consumer of knowledge into an active creator capable of planning and predicting their independent work, who can take initiative, express a problem, analyze ways to solve it, obtain an optimal result and prove its correctness. In this regard, it can be said that the training of students in a higher education institution requires the use of teaching technologies that ensure the formation of a professionally competent, socially active, creative independent person. Development of intellectual skills in a goal-oriented manner becomes the most important task of the student mathematician. These skills are one of the key competencies that ensure professional mobility and flexibility of students. In other words, the competence-based approach, which ensures the formation of professional competence of a specialist, serves as one of the conditions for training a competitive specialist.

Scientist I.A. The introduction of Zimnyaya's competence-based approach to education is conditioned not only by the change of the educational paradigm that is taking place today, but also by global changes in the world - changes in the structure and character of the labor market, the computerization of all spheres of social and industrial life of our country, and the formation of a new technogenic civilization. , cannot be disagreed with [1, 3].

In our opinion, increasing the level of competitiveness of higher education graduates in the labor market and the level of their professional education aimed at international standards is a key factor in the transition to a competency-based approach. In this regard, new demands are placed on the graduates of HEIs, and the demands are not on the detailed knowledge of the future specialists, but on their competences. Thus, on the basis of a competent approach in education, it is primarily intended to plan the results of teaching. It is also observed in the state educational standards of higher education [1]. They focus primarily on graduate competencies and, secondly, on educational resources and content.

The works of the following pedagogues can be cited as confirmation of this opinion: I.Ya. Lerner, M.N. Skatkin and others. Their work was aimed at clarifying the issues of knowledge acquisition and methods of generalization of activity, but such focus is not decisive or decisive for

education, and in this regard it was hardly used. In addition, Yu.K. Babansky [2, 3], E.N. Kabanova-Meller, Yu.M. Kolyagin, V.T. Kudryavtsev, E.A. The theory of competence formation reflected in the works of scholars such as Millerian did not receive due attention, and due to the appearance of the term "competence" in the Anglo-American educational environment, and because it was considered almost synonymous with "skills", this term was quickly introduced into widespread use in the field.

I.A. Zimnyaya divides the period of formation of competence-based approach in education into several stages. The scientist considers the first stage to have passed in the 70s of the 20th century. during this period, the concept of "competence" was put into circulation in the field of pedagogy and the basis for understanding the differences between the concepts of "competence" and "competency" which are being studied today [1,2].

The time limits of the second stage of the competence-based approach in education were defined by scientist I.A. Zimnyaya believed that it happened in the 80s and 90s of the 20th century. This stage is distinguished by the use of the concept of "competency" in the theory and practice of teaching a language, especially a foreign language, and teaching communication [1]. It is during this period that the essence and content of the concept of "competence" is developed. Competence means J. Raven understands the special ability of a person, which includes narrowly specialized knowledge, skills and ways of thinking, and the willingness to take responsibility for one's actions, necessary to perform an action in a specific/specific field of science [2]. In addition, it is possible to include in this period the research and separation of different types of competences, taking into account the goals and final results of the training. For example, J. Raven distinguishes 37 types of competencies and compares them with competencies [3].

In addition to the difference in emphases on learning outcomes of competency-based and IFC-based approaches, we will try to distinguish some other differences.

First, the difference in students' perceptions of the ways of forming their value goals/orientations and personal qualities is significant.

In the conditions of the traditional approach to education, the formation of the values of students is carried out by acquiring and increasing the volume of knowledge, and on the basis of the competent approach, it is possible to achieve this at the expense of their personal experience of being able to get out of problematic situations independently.

Secondly, the difference in independent work in competence-based and cognitive approaches is conditioned by different ways of knowing the educational material. In the traditional (cognitive) approach, students often do independent work according to the detailed illustrated/described educational material presented in a more understandable, convenient form for them. In this case, a high degree of algorithmization of students' academic-independent work/actions is characteristic. Independent implementation of the algorithms written by the teacher should lead to the formation and strengthening of practical skills in students. During the performance of independent work, the student's activity is regulated, and he himself remains in the leading position, and this develops the executive discipline of the student conditioned by external coercion. However, it is impossible to talk about the formation of competence for independent education at all. The habit of working/following the algorithm taught by zero has a negative effect on the student's independent acquisition of one or another professional competence.

In contrast to the cognitive approach, the competency-based approach does not provide detailed instructional material for students' independent work. The student is given a detailed

statement/description of the task to be performed and the results of his/her independent work/actions. It is necessary for the student to search for information from various sources, to independently select methodological, scientific and other materials to acquire certain knowledge, skills and abilities that serve as a means of solving a specific/concrete practical task or problem situation. Here, the student's independent organization of his study time is an important aspect, and this limits the standardization of the independent work process to a minimum. Independent work organized under the conditions of a competent approach allows students to develop research skills, to develop the competence of independent work activities that will undoubtedly help them master the knowledge and technologies necessary for their future activities, and thereby help them to form professional competence.

Thirdly, the principles and stages of work organization in OTM are focused on productive/productive and creative processes, rather than reproduction, in contrast to the occupational re-based approach. Simple memorization and repetition gives way to creative and practical work.

Fourth, the difference between the competent approach and the approach to doing is that the number of independent supervision is independent in teaching.

In the approach based on BMK, a continuous review of the entire process of independent work is carried out; the teacher evaluates both its intermediate and final results. In this case, the student does not have a serious need for independent control of acquired knowledge and independent assessment. A competent approach to the organization of independent work in higher education allows the teacher to control the direct result of independent work of students [3].

Also, on his own initiative. the student performs independent control of his independent activity, evaluates intermediate results and identifies final results, and this helps to increase the level of awareness of his knowledge acquisition and application and is directly related to the manifestation of his activity [4]. Here, the teacher acts as a tutor - that is, a consultant on specific questions and problems that arise during the student's independent assignment. The student's objective/biased assessment of his knowledge gives him the opportunity to make corrections to his work in order to achieve the results of his independent work in accordance with the set requirements. The student's ability to make adjustments to his/her actions in order to achieve the best results is an indicator of self-regulation and implies a certain level of competence of the future specialist.

Fifth, the undoubted negative aspect of the bachelor's approach to the organization of students' independent work is that the student's critical thinking, creativity, individuality, creativity, reflection, etc. such qualities are not fully taken into account, and in the competent approach, the personality of the student is placed at the head of higher education.

Finally, we emphasize that the importance of the studied approaches in the attitude of higher school teachers is no less than the above. In the knowledge-based approach, the teacher acts as a kind of carrier of "objective knowledge" that needs to be imparted to the student. In modern conditions, the HE teacher should create conditions in which the student can realize his abilities, develop critical thinking, show initiative and independence, learn the skills of cognitive activity and independent work, and, ultimately, the result of education in a higher educational institution. to form the key competencies.

In our opinion, the knowledge-based approach in the process of organizing independent work in HEIs can be relied upon only in the first years of training students, and this allows them to develop executive discipline.

After that, a gradual transition from a knowledge-based approach to a competent approach is necessary, and in this process, students must perform algorithms, "forcibly" acquire knowledge, skills and skills, control the entire process of the student's independent work, and gradually acquire the knowledge and skills necessary for the student. Independent control and independent assessment of their knowledge, and on the part of the teacher, it is replaced by control of the direct result of the student's independent activity (changes to doing). With this, it is inevitable that a competent approach to the organization of the last re-independent work of the student's education at the Higher Education Institution will be a priority. It helps the student to develop qualities that allow him to independently acquire professional knowledge and relevant functional skills when necessary [4, 5].

CONCLUSION

Thus, today, the organization of independent work of students based on a competent approach occupies a worthy place in the system of organization of the higher education process.

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